

EFFECTIVENESS OF MUSCLE ENERGY TECHNIQUE AND CAPSULAR STRETCHING IN PAIN REDUCTION AND IMPROVEMENT OF ROM AMONG PATIENT WITH ADHESIVE CAPSULITIS

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Abstract

Adhesive capsulitis is painful condition in which both active or passive movement loss and formation of contractures of glenohumeral joint occur in this condition. Adhesive capsulitis commonly present in older population. In this study Muscle energy technique and capsular stretching used to treat adhesive capsulitis. In METs, Muscle contact isometrically by using his own energy. And capsular stretching is a passive stretching used to lengthen up shortened soft tissue by using some external force. The main purpose of this study to compare the effectiveness of MET and capsular stretching among patient with adhesive capsulitis. **Aims and Objectives:** To compare the effectiveness of Muscle energy technique and capsular stretching in pain reduction and range of motion improvement among patients with (primary) adhesive capsulitis. **Methodology:** A randomized clinical trial was performed .30 patients of adhesive capsulitis included in this study. Subjects were taken from Allied Hospital, MTH and Aziz Fatima Hospital. Subjects were divided into two groups A or B. Hot pack given to both groups for 10 minutes as a baseline treatment. Group A was given the Muscle Energy Techniques and Group B was given capsular stretching. The primary outcome was pain and ROM. The secondary outcome was shoulder pain and disability or Upper extremity functional scale. The measurements were performed at baseline, following three- weeks of intervention. **Conclusion:** Capsular stretching and muscle energy technique are effective in the management of frozen shoulder. Both techniques help to improve ROM and reduce pain in adhesive capsulitis patients. Both techniques showed better improvement in reduction of functional disabilities in adhesive capsulitis patients.

INTRODUCTION

Glenohumeral joint present in shoulder joint .It is a ball and socket joint which allow greater mobility of shoulder. Muscles present in shoulder allow movement in different direction most likely flexion, abduction, external rotation and internal rotation. Scapula is the central bony structure, all muscles of shoulder interconnected at scapular region. Articular surface of glenohumeral joint is present at the lateral side of scapula. Rotator cuff muscles are primary group of muscles which provide support to the shoulder joint. Supraspinatus, infraspinatus, teres minor and subscapular are rotator cuff muscles. Other muscles include the pectoralis major, pectoralis minor, the deltoids, trapezius, and the serratus anterior that forms shoulder girdle (1).

Function of these muscles relates with the deltoid muscle function. Strengthening exercise of deltoid provides beneficiary effect to strengthen up of rotator cuff or all shoulder muscles in kinetic chain(2). Painful condition of shoulder is adhesive capsulitis, as result of this condition loss of glenohumeral joint ranges .It results from contraction of the glenohumeral joint capsule .Frozen shoulder also known as adhesive capsulitis or other related condition with joint ranges loss. Adhesive capsulitis is basically a self-limiting condition (3). In adhesive capsulitis, there is loss of both active and passive range of motion of shoulder joint. Patients present with painful stiff shoulder which is mainly diagnosed with frozen shoulder. Adhesive capsulitis is a specific pathologic in which chronic inflammation of the capsule produces capsular thickening, fibrosis, and adherence to the anatomic neck of the humerus. The contracted, then adherent capsule produces pain, particularly when abruptly stretched, and produces restriction to motion(4).

Primary adhesive capsulitis happens suddenly without any particular cause. Primary adhesive capsulitis occur due to chronic inflammatory response with fibroelastic proliferation, which occur may be an unusual response from the immune system. Secondary adhesive capsulitis occurs as result of injury or linked with other diseases likely, diabetes, CVA which have required prolong recovery or limited outcome measures(6). AC is divided into

three stages : painful freezing phase(10-36 weeks), frozen phase (4-12 months), and determination phase(12-42 months), later by Neviser, AC is divided into four stages : pre adhesive stage pain occur in both active or passive movements, freezing stage (3-9 months) extreme level of pain , frozen stage(9-15 months) there is least pain but shoulder ranges limited and thawing stage (15-24 months)existent with slowly regaining and restore shoulder mobility(7).

In literature, three stages of frozen shoulder included freezing, frozen and thawing stage, symptoms of all these stages lasting 30 months. Average range of frozen stage of shoulder is 98° abduction, 117° flexion, 33° external rotation and 18° of internal rotation with abducted shoulder to 90°. Shoulder muscles imbalance due to limited mobility of shoulder joint (8).

Scapular movements based on shoulder rehabilitation. Scientific studies shows patients with adhesive capsulitis having decreased scapular movements, particularly increased superior rotation or decreased external rotation and also increase glenohumeral joint mobility which is important for rehabilitation program(9).

Capsular tension is important problem of frozen shoulder most common anterior or posterior capsular tension. Glenohumeral internal rotation decreases in posterior capsular tension and so the glenohumeral rhythm. Posterior capsular stretching has positive effects on ROM of the joint, decreasing the adhesions and improvement of collagen (10).

Peak onset of adhesive capsulitis in age above 50 years and it is common in females as compared to males. There was less evidence available in literature which showed the comparison of effectiveness of METs and capsular stretching among adhesive capsulitis patients. This study was find that which technique is more effective in adhesive capsulitis patients. This study was also compare the effects of both techniques on both genders among adhesive capsulitis patients.

METHODOLOGY

This interventional study used a randomized clinical trial design and was conducted over four months at Madina Teaching Hospital, Aziz Fatima Hospital,

and Allied Hospital in Faisalabad. A total of 30 participants aged 40–60 years with adhesive capsulitis were enrolled using purposive sampling and then randomly allocated into two groups: Group A (Muscle Energy Techniques) and Group B (capsular stretching). Treatment duration was three weeks, and data were analyzed using SPSS version 20. Inclusion criteria included both males and females in stage 2 or 3 of primary adhesive capsulitis with symptoms such as restricted shoulder movement and night or resting pain. Exclusion criteria involved patients with rotator cuff rupture, secondary adhesive capsulitis, trauma-related stiffness, tendon calcification, or glenohumeral joint rupture. Informed consent was obtained from all participants. Data collection tools included the Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), Shoulder Pain and Disability Index (SPADI), Upper Extremity Functional Index (UEFI), and a goniometer to assess range of motion. Primary outcomes focused on pain reduction and improvement in shoulder range of motion using the

NPRS. Secondary outcomes included shoulder function and disability measured by SPADI and UEFI. All patients received a 10-minute moist hot pack as a warm-up before treatment sessions. Group A received METs for shoulder flexion, abduction, external and internal rotation, performed in 3 sets of 5 repetitions each session for three weeks. Group B received anterior, posterior, and antero-inferior capsular stretching, with each stretch held for 30 seconds. Both groups received their respective interventions along with baseline therapy.

Results

The study sample consisted of 30 participants, equally divided into two intervention groups. The age range was 40–60 years, with a mean age of 50.0 ± 6.81 years. Female participants were predominant (63.33%), reflecting the higher prevalence of adhesive capsulitis in women.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N = 30)

Characteristic	Group A (MET)	Group B (Capsular Stretching)	Total
Number of Participants	15	15	30
Age (Mean \pm SD)	50.2 ± 6.9	49.8 ± 6.7	50.0 ± 6.81
Gender (Male/Female)	5 / 10	6 / 9	11 / 19

In both treatment groups, significant improvements were observed in all outcome measures, including pain reduction, shoulder function, and range of motion (ROM). The Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) showed significant within-group improvements ($p < 0.05$), with Group A showing a greater reduction in pain intensity. The Shoulder Pain and Disability Index (SPADI) scores also

decreased significantly in both groups, but Group B showed a larger absolute improvement. Upper Extremity Functional Index (UEFI) scores improved significantly in both groups, indicating enhanced functional ability. Repeated measures ANOVA revealed substantial gains in shoulder ROM (flexion, abduction, and external rotation) across pre, mid, and post-treatment phases, with p -values < 0.001 .

Table 2: Treatment Outcomes of Group A (MET) and Group B (Capsular Stretching)

Outcome Measure	Group A (Mean \pm SD)	Group B (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
NPRS (Pain Score)	Pre: 6.73 ± 1.33 Post: 3.06 ± 0.70	Pre: 6.80 ± 1.08 Post: 3.93 ± 1.33	.000
SPADI (Disability Index)	Pre-Post Difference: 21.67 ± 17.20	Pre-Post Difference: 43.48 ± 6.65	.000
UEFI (Functional Scale)	Pre-Post Change: $+15.33 \pm 4.98$	Pre-Post Change: $+16.93 \pm 5.88$.000
Shoulder Flexion ROM (°)	Pre: 99.0 Post: 142.7	(Combined mean values used)	.000
Shoulder Abduction ROM (°)	Pre: 97.7 Post: 147.3		.000
Shoulder External Rotation ROM (°)	Pre: 37.7 Post: 71.3		.000

The results of this study conclude that both Muscle Energy Techniques (MET) and capsular stretching

significantly improved pain, shoulder range of motion, and upper extremity function in patients

with adhesive capsulitis. However, MET was more effective in reducing pain intensity, while capsular stretching showed greater improvement in functional disability scores. Range of motion improved significantly in both groups across all measured movements. These findings indicate that both interventions are clinically beneficial, but the selection may be tailored based on individual patient needs and targeted outcomes.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to compare the effects of Muscle Energy Technique (MET) and capsular stretching in managing pain and improving range of motion (ROM) in patients with stage 2 and 3 adhesive capsulitis. A total of 30 participants, aged between 40–60 years, were selected using purposive sampling and randomly allocated into two groups. Group A received MET with conventional therapy, and Group B received capsular stretching with conventional therapy, three times per week for three weeks. Primary outcome measures included NPRS and SPADI, while ROM was evaluated through goniometer readings at pre, mid, and post-treatment intervals.

The findings demonstrated significant improvements in pain, ROM, and functional scores in both groups. Group A, treated with MET, showed a greater reduction in pain levels (mean NPRS post-treatment = 3.06 ± 0.73 , $p = 0.000$), while Group B, treated with capsular stretching, also exhibited improvement (mean NPRS post-treatment = 3.93 ± 1.33 , $p = 0.000$). Independent *t*-test confirmed significant differences between both groups for pain reduction ($p = 0.03$ for Group A; $p = 0.034$ for Group B).

Repeated measures ANOVA showed a significant increase in ROM in both groups across shoulder flexion, abduction, and external rotation ($p = 0.000$). Both interventions led to notable gains in functional outcomes, with SPADI and UEFS scores improving significantly post-treatment.

Previous studies also support these findings. MET has been found effective in reducing pain and improving joint mobility due to its neuromuscular and post-isometric relaxation effects (11). Similarly, studies have shown that posterior capsular stretching and mobilization contribute significantly to ROM and functional outcomes (12, 13). Spencer technique

and other manual therapies, like Mulligan's Mobilization and PIR, have also been demonstrated as effective alternatives in managing adhesive capsulitis (14).

Conclusion

Both Muscle Energy Technique and capsular stretching are effective for reducing pain and improving ROM in adhesive capsulitis. MET demonstrated slightly superior outcomes in pain reduction. These findings support the clinical utility of both interventions for short-term management.

Strengths

- The study utilized multiple outcome measures: NPRS, SPADI, UEFS, and goniometry.
- It highlights a rarely explored comparison between MET and capsular stretching.

Limitations

- Small sample size.
- Absence of a control group.
- No long-term follow-up.

Future Recommendations

- Conduct studies with larger sample sizes.
- Extend the duration of intervention beyond three weeks.
- Include long-term follow-up to assess sustained effects.
- Apply age-specific inclusion criteria to enhance specificity.

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